

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
**EDUCATION AND
TECHNOLOGY (AJET)**

ISSN: 2832-9481 (ONLINE)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 2 (2022)

Indexed in

PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

Learning Styles and Learning Abilities of Grade 6 Pupils in Dealing with Modular Learning

Irish C. Camat¹, Angel Grace G. Caro¹, Mary Grace C. Catahum¹, Hanna Raquel C. Jabido¹, Kris D. Reyes¹,
Angel Lhi D. Alcalde^{1*}, Angelo P. Florague¹, Ma. Yzelle M. Bayog¹, Ivy N. Macagba¹

Article Information

Received: August 09, 2022

Accepted: August 16, 2022

Published: August 18, 2022

Keywords

Learning Styles, Learning Abilities, Grade 6 Pupils, Modular Learning

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the learning styles and learning abilities of grade 6 pupils in dealing with modular learning. A descriptive design was used in this study. The survey was conducted in Lt. Andres Calungsud Elementary School to 30 elementary pupils who are enrolled in modular learning for School Year 2021-2022 and the majority of them were male pupils. A Researcher-made survey questionnaire was used in data gathering. Frequency and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation, megastat were used in treating the data. The study revealed that the pupils have difficulty dealing with terms in their modules. Data show that the respondents got the highest mean in visual learning style interpreted as Often (M=2.60) and the lowest mean in auditory learning style. The respondent's learning style in reading/writing got the lowest overall mean Sometimes (OM=1.94). The study found out that the highest problem encountered by the students in dealing with modular learning is confused by words. Data show that the respondent's Digital - age Literacy type Learning Abilities got the highest mean of Sometimes (M=2.17) in the item "I feel comfortable using digital devices". The respondent's learning ability in problem-based thinking and problem-solving got the lowest mean of Sometimes. The Elementary pupils are highly satisfied with how teachers showed interest in helping students to develop personal skills and qualities. Moreover, the respondents are least satisfied with how they received sufficient advice and guidance in relation to the module. Finally, there is a significant difference in the learning styles and learning abilities of respondents.

INTRODUCTION

Education is constantly changing. As we better understand learning methods, theories evolve, and new ones emerge. Current and future teachers must be trained to be ready to teach students every day. An important part of teacher training is keeping up with these changes. While the Learning Style Model is still important to know, keeping up to date with research related to learning and teaching is even more important for educators. All young children learn through meaningful hands-on experiences - by touching, making, and moving. And children also learn by seeing and hearing. By observing a child, one will begin to identify strengths and interests that talk about the child's preferred learning style (Abilitypath, 2020).

Educators in the United States and around the world have embraced the concept of learning styles. According to studies, 89% of teachers believe that instruction should be tailored to a student's preferred learning style (Newton & Salvi, 2020).

Modular learning is the most popular type of distance learning. In the Philippines, this learning modality is currently used by all public schools College of Education because according to a survey conducted by the Department of Education (DepEd), learning through printed and digital modules emerged as the most preferred distance learning method of parents with children who are enrolled this academic year (Bernardo, J 2020). This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where the internet is not accessible for online learning. Thus, the teacher is responsible for keeping track of the student's

progress.

Learning styles are terms that describe how people gather, sort through, interpret, organize, draw conclusions from, and store information for later use. The student-centered approach promotes greater consistency between the teacher and the student, both of whom have a role to play in the learning process. While teachers retain authority, they now serve as facilitators, coaches, and mentors to their students (Lathan, 2021). Teachers must consider the students preferred learning styles for this approach to be effective. Students who are aware of their learning styles will have no trouble dealing with this approach.

The rate at which a student can learn is usually determined by his or her academic ability. A student's lower ability, and thus a slower rate of learning, is not necessarily a sign of future failure. Teachers should be aware that a student with less ability may excel in more specific areas than his or her peers.

Students with a medium ability score may be less motivated to learn, especially if they lack confidence in group situations. While they may not be as shy as low-ability students, these students may benefit from learning materials that include increasingly difficult tasks as they gain confidence.

Western Sydney University (2020) refers digital to literacy as the abilities required to live, learn, and work in a society where communication and information are increasingly provided through digital platforms such as the internet, social media, and mobile devices. When you're dealing with a lot of information in numerous formats, you'll need to

¹ Notre Dame of Midsayap College, Midsayap, Cotabato, Philippines.

* Corresponding author's e-mail: delacruzangellhi@gmail.com

improve your critical thinking abilities. Searching, sorting, assessing, applying, and producing knowledge all demand you to think critically of digital literacy is communication. The capacity to clearly convey your thoughts, ask appropriate questions, maintain respect, and create trust in virtual environments is just as vital as when interacting in person. You'll also need practical knowledge of how to use technology ethically and sustainably to access, manage, alter, and create data. While you're a university student, digital literacy is extremely important. It will also be extremely useful when you enter the professional world. You'll be expected to communicate with people in digital environments, use information appropriately, and collaborate on new ideas and products at work. Above all, as the digital landscape continues to develop at a rapid speed, you'll need to preserve your digital identity and wellbeing.

Powerschool (2021) describes it as the capacity to find, analyze, use, share, and produce content using online resources such as eBooks, websites, social media, and videos is referred to as digital literacy. Digital literacy helps students learn by laying a strong foundation for them to engage with online materials and effectively use digital technologies in the learning process. Many children have access to a personal or school-issued device—a phone, tablet, or computer—that allows them to access material from all across the internet. Teachers and parents must assist children navigate and engage effectively with the digital world as the usage of digital resources in the curriculum grows.

Modular learning is a type of distance education that makes use of self-study modules. These self-learning modules are based on the Department of Education's most essential learning competencies (MELCS). Individualized instruction is provided through modular distance learning, which allows students to use self-learning modules (SLMs) in print or digital format/electronic copy, depending on their needs. Other resources such as Learner's Materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other study materials are available to Modular Distance Learning students. Module distance learning, according to Mark Anthony Llego (2020), entails students "learning at their own pace and using self-learning modules" (SLMs). Teachers are usually responsible for providing appropriate learning materials. Students can, however, download electronic copies of these materials to their computer, tablet PC, or smartphone.

As home facilitators, parents play a critical role. Their primary function in modular learning is to establish a connection with the child and to guide them. (2020, FlipScience). In their study on the effectiveness of learning in the use of learning modules against students learning outcomes, Rahmawati, Lestari, and Umam (2019) found that students using modules had better average mathematics learning outcomes than students who did not use the module.

According to a study conducted by Ambayon (2020) on the modular-based approach and students' achievement

in literature, the performance of college students in literature who used the modular approach improved from poor to excellent achievement, while students who did not use the modular approach improved from poor to fair achievement.

Another study by Oparina & Rakova (2018) on the Modular Approach to Teaching and Learning English Grammar in Technical Universities found that the module approach is effective in improving students' knowledge. Its modular approach to English grammar teaching and learning has been found to be effective in terms of teaching and increasing students' understanding and critical thinking.

Valencia (2020) Modular Approach in Teaching Science 10 found that when students were taught using a modular approach, their test results improved significantly, and they were described as competent. This indicates that the strategy has proven to be effective in raising students' academic achievement.

Modular learning can take the form of printed or digital materials. Modular distance learning, according to Mark Antony Llego (2020), is defined as learners learning at their own pace, in their own way, and using self-learning modules (SLMs). Other learning resources such as learners' materials, textbooks, activity sheets, study guides, and other learning materials can be printed/digitized format/electronic copy that is appropriate for learners.

Learners can use a computer, tablet PC, or smartphone to access electronic copies of learning materials. E-learning materials, including offline E-books, can be delivered via CDs, DVDs, USB storage, and computer-based applications.

The teacher oversees keeping track of the students' progress. While students may seek assistance from them via email, telephone, text messaging/instant messaging, and other means. If a learner requires remediation or assistance in his or her module, teachers will make home visits. Any member of the family or other community stakeholders can help. Furthermore, modular learning is a type of distance learning that employs self-learning modules (SLM) and adheres to the DepEd's most essential learning competencies (Diaz, n.d.).

The use of modules promotes independent learning. One of the advantages of using modules for instruction is that students develop better self-study or learning skills. Students actively participated in understanding the concepts presented in the module. They gain a sense of responsibility as they complete the tasks in the module. The students' progress on their own with little or no help from others (Dangle, Sumaoang 2020).

Student-centered learning is one of the methods for establishing a more stable relationship between the teacher and the student by involving both parties in the learning process. Teachers are increasingly serving as facilitators, coaches, and advisors to students (Lathan, 2021). For this strategy to work, teachers must consider the students' preferred learning styles. Students who are aware of their learning styles will be able to cope with

this approach more easily. Both teaching and learning styles have an impact on student development and achievement. As a result, researchers are concentrating their efforts on determining students' learning styles, especially considering the New Normal. According to results from a reading assessment given to first- through fourth graders across the country, the development of oral reading fluency – the ability to read aloud quickly and accurately – slowed significantly in spring 2020. The streamlined K-12 curriculum, reduced competencies by nearly half, and adopted various learning modalities based on parental preferences. Modular (printed or digitized) instruction, online learning, radio and television-based instruction, or a combination of these options are available (blended learning).

During last year's enrollment, DepEd conducted a survey of parents, and found that 80% of them preferred the printed modular learning modality for their children. Mr. Masapol explained that it reflects most Filipinos' lack of access to other modes of transportation. The teacher can be reached by e-mail, phone, text message, or instant messaging, among other methods. If possible, the teacher will visit students who need remediation or assistance at their homes (Llego, n.d.). Students, parents, and guardians will receive printed modules from teachers or local government officials. Parents have become educators' partners as education is no longer confined to the classroom. Parents play an important role as home facilitators. In modular learning, their primary role is to establish a connection with the child and to guide them. (FlipScience, 2020).

METHODS

This chapter presents the research design, locale of the study, respondents, sampling design, instrumentation, validity and reliability of the instrument, data gathering procedure, and statistical tool and treatment of data.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive design to determine the learning styles and learning abilities of Grade 6 pupils in dealing with modular learning. It also looked at the connections to analyze the effects between learning styles and learning abilities of the respondents of Lt. Andres Calungsod Elementary School in Poblacion 8, Midsayap, Cotabato.

Locale and Respondents to the Study

The research was conducted in Poblacion 8, Midsayap wherein the Lt. Andres Calungsod Elementary School is located. Poblacion 8 is one of the 57 barangays in the Municipality of Midsayap North Cotabato.

It is in the southern part of the Municipality. This public school is located about 0.32 kilometers away from the national highway. The respondents of the study were the 30 Grade 6 pupils of section Rizal in Lt. Andres Calungsod Elementary School for the school year 2021-2022.

Sampling Design

The researcher employed purposive sampling method. For specific cases, purposive sampling is a viable option since it selects instances using expert judgment or with a specific goal in mind. When a difficult-to-reach population needs to be measured, the most common method is to utilize targeted sampling. Thus, for this study, the respondents were the 30 Grade 6 pupils, section Rizal. They were chosen out of the three sections consisting of 103 pupils at Lt. Andres Calungsod Elementary School. All of Section Rizal were requested to act as respondents of this study.

Instrumentation

The researcher made an adopted survey questionnaire as the main data-gathering instrument. The items of the questionnaires were taken from the different sample survey questionnaires in modular learning. The instrument was divided into four parts. Part 1 was designed to determine the demographic profile of the students consisting of age and sex. Part II contains the Learning Style in Dealing with Modular Learning, Part III contains the Learning Ability in Dealing with Modular Learning, Part IV contains the Problem in Dealing with Modular Learning; and Part V contains questions regarding the Effectiveness in Dealing with Modular Learning.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The questionnaire underwent a series of checking. It was thoroughly reviewed by the adviser, proof-reader, and statistician to ensure validity, clarity of instruction, the correctness of grammatical construction, and fitness of content. To further validate the items in the survey questionnaire, the researchers conducted a pilot test on 10 Grade 6 pupils who were studying in Katingawan SDA Elementary school in Poblacion 8, Midsayap, North Cotabato. The statistical tool of Cronbach's Alpha was determined and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.98, an indication that the instrument is reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following steps have been conducted during the gathering of data.

The researchers sent a letter of intent addressed to the Barangay Captain of Poblacion 8, Midsayap, Cotabato, and to the principal in – charge of Calungsod, Elementary school in Poblacion 8, Midsayap. In addition, the researcher also requested the total number of enrolled Grade 6 pupils for the school year 2021-2022. Then, the schedule for the courtesy call was set with the barangay officials stating the purpose of the study. Health and safety protocols were properly observed during this part of the study. Moreover, the content of the research was explained personally to the respondents. These include the ethical considerations and data privacy protocol with regard to their participation. The schedule for the conduct of the survey has been set. The survey was conducted house-to-house by asking permission to the

respective parents/guardian of the respondents. During the survey, the questions indicated in the instrument were explained further by the researcher using the respondent's native language.

Statistical Tools and Treatment of Data

The researcher used the appropriate statistical tools for each problem statement. Frequency count and percentage distribution were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age and section. For problems 1, 2, 3, and 4 the weighted mean and standard deviation were computed to identify the learning style and ability of grade 6 pupils in dealing with modular learning, the effectiveness, and the problems encountered by the Grade 6 pupils in Lt. Andres Calungsod Elementary school.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the result of the profile of respondents. Data show the frequency and percentage distribution in terms of age and sex. Among the 30

Table 1: Profile of Respondents

Profile of the Respondents	f	%
Age		
12	18	60
13	12	40
Total	30	100
Sex		
Male	16	53.33
Female	14	46.67
Total	30	100

respondents, 18 or 60 % are 12 years old while 12 or 40% ages 13years old. In terms of the respondent's sex, 18 or 53.33 are male while 14 or 46.67 % are female.

This chapter presents the result of the Learning Styles. According to the data, the respondents indicated that the highest mean in visual learning style is Often (M=2.60) with the statement "Using flash cards help me to retain

Table 2: Learning Style

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
A. Visual			
1. I learn best when I am shown how to do something, and I have the opportunity to do it.	1.83	0.53	Sometimes
2. It helps me to look at a person while listening. It keeps my focus.	1.93	0.64	Sometimes
3. Using flash cards help me to retain materials for test.	2.60	0.62	Often
Overall	2.12	0.60	Sometimes
B. Auditory			
1. I can remember best by listening to a lecture that includes information, explanation, and discussion.	2.03	0.72	Sometimes
2. I remember things I hear, rather than things that I see or read.	2.17	0.38	Sometimes
3. I follow oral directions better than written ones.	3.00	0.00	Often
Overall	2.40	0.37	Often
C. Reading and writing			
1. I remember something better if I write it down.	2.00	0.64	Sometimes
2. I can remember best by writing things down several times.	1.93	0.78	Sometimes
3. I prefer obtaining information about an interesting subject by reading about it.	1.90	0.66	Sometimes
Overall	1.94	0.70	Sometimes
D. Kinesthetic			
1. I like to move around while I am listening or talking.	2.00	0.59	Sometimes
2. I like to touch things in order to learn about them.	2.30	0.84	Sometimes
3. I enjoy learning with my hands or making things.	2.20	0.85	Sometimes
Overall	2.17	0.76	Sometimes
Grand Mean/SD	2.16	0.60	Sometimes

Scale	Range	Description
1	1 < 1.67	Never
2	1.67 – 2.33	Sometimes
3	2.34 – 3.00	Often

materials for test".

Learning Style

Data show that the respondents signified that the highest mean in visual learning style interpreted as Often (M=2.60) is the statement "Using flash cards help me to retain materials for test." While the lowest mean in visual

learning style is interpreted as Sometimes (M=1.83) which states "I learn best when I am shown how to do something, and I have the opportunity to do it." In the auditory type of learning, the item which got the highest mean was interpreted as Sometimes (M=3.00) surveyed "I follow oral directions better than written ones". While the item which got the lowest mean was interpreted as Sometimes (M=2.03) is the item "I can remember best by listening to a lecture that includes information, explanation, and discussion". Moreover, in the reading/writing type of learning style, the item, "I remember something better if I write it down got the highest

mean of Sometimes (M=2.00). The item which got the lowest mean was interpreted as Sometimes (M=1.90) is the statement “I prefer obtaining information about an interesting subject by reading about it.” In the kinesthetic type of learning style, the researchers signified that the respondents got the highest mean Sometimes (M=2.30) in the item “I like to touch things in order to learn about them” while they got the lowest mean of Sometimes (M=2.00) in the item “I like to move around while I am listening or talking”. Furthermore, they signified that the

respondent’s learning style in auditory got the highest overall mean Often (OM=2.40) while the respondent’s learning style in reading/writing got the lowest overall mean Sometimes (OM=1.94) surveyed in Poblacion 8, Midsayap, Cotabato.

This chapter presents the result of Learning Abilities. Data show that the respondents’ Digital - age - Literacy type Learning Abilities got the highest mean of Sometimes (M=2.17) interpreted as “I feel comfortable using digital devices”.

Table 3: Learning Abilities

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
A. Digital Age Literacy			
1. I enjoy digital devices.	1.97	0.72	Sometimes
2. I am aware of various types of digital devices.	2.03	0.67	Sometimes
3. I feel comfortable using digital devices.	2.17	0.70	Sometimes
Overall	2.06	0.70	Sometimes
B. Problem – based Thinking and Problem Solving			
1. I am good at working and solving jigsaw puzzles and mazes.	2.00	0.37	Sometimes
2. I solve a problem by focusing on its main point.	2.03	0.72	Sometimes
3. I am sure that I am able to solve even a difficult problem.	1.87	0.51	Sometimes
Overall	1.97	0.53	Sometimes
C. Creativity			
1. I am skillful with enjoy developing making graphs and charts.	1.63	0.56	Never
2. My notes, hand-outs, and other school materials are carefully organized.	2.00	0.59	Sometimes
3. I look familiar concepts as well as ideas that sparks my interest as I read.	2.13	0.57	Sometimes
Overall	1.92	0.57	Sometimes
Grand Mean/SD	1.98	0.60	Sometimes

Scale	Range	Description
1	1 < 1.67	Never
2	1.67 – 2.33	Sometimes
3	2.34 – 3.00	Often

Learning Abilities

Data show that the respondents Digital - age - Literacy type Learning Abilities got the highest mean of Sometime (M=2.17) in the item “I feel comfortable using digital devices”. While the item “I enjoyed digital devices” got the lowest mean is of (M=1.97) interpreted as Sometimes. In problem-based thinking and problem solving, the researchers signified that the respondents got the highest mean of Sometimes (M=2.03) in the item “I solve the problem by focusing on its main point”. Moreover, they signified that the respondents got the lowest mean of Sometimes (M=1.87) in the item “I am sure that I am able to solve even a difficult problem “.In the creativity type of learning ability, the statement “I look for familiar concepts as well as ideas that spark my interest as I read” got the highest mean of (M=2.13) interpreted as Sometimes surveyed They signified that the respondents got the lowest mean of Sometimes (M=1.63) in the item “I am skillful with and enjoy developing and making graphs and chart.” Furthermore, the researchers signified that the respondent’s learning ability in digital age literacy got the highest overall mean of Sometimes (OM= 2.06) while the respondent’s learning ability in problem -based thinking and problem-solving got the lowest mean of Sometimes (OM=1.97).

This chapter presents the result of Effectiveness in Dealing with Modular Learning. Data show that the respondents signified that the specified items for Effectiveness in Dealing with Modular Learning got the highest mean of Sometimes (M=3.00) which states “The module helped to develop my personal skills and qualities.”.

Effectiveness in Dealing with Modular Learning

Data show that the respondents signified that the specified items for Effectiveness in Dealing with Modular Learning got the highest mean is Sometimes (M=3.00) with the statement “The module helped to develop my personal skills and qualities.”. They signified that the respondents got the lowest mean of Sometimes (M=1.80) in the statement “Modular learning helped save time and energy on travel to and from school”. Furthermore, they signified that the respondents Sometimes (OM=2.33) surveyed in Poblacion 8 Midsayap, Cotabato.

This chapter presents the result of Problems in Dealing with Modular Learning. Data show that the respondents signified that the specified items for Problem in Dealing with Modular Learning got the highest mean of Sometimes (M=2.23) with the statement “Have words confused”.

Problems in Dealing with Modular Learning

Data show that the respondents signified that the specified items for Problem in Dealing with Modular Learning got the highest mean is Sometimes (M=2.23)

Table 4: Effectiveness in Dealing with Modular Learning

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
1. I received timely and helpful feedback on my learning in the module.	2.23	0.43	Sometimes
2. The teaching on the module helped me to learn.	2.17	0.38	Sometimes
3. Modular learning helped save time and energy on travel to and from school.	1.80	0.55	Sometimes
4. The module helped to develop my personal skills and qualities.	3.00	0.00	Sometimes
5. The learning activities on the module helped me to learn.	2.33	0.48	Sometimes
Overall	2.33	0.48	Sometimes
3. I am sure that I am able to solve even a difficult problem.	1.87	0.51	Sometimes
Overall	1.97	0.53	Sometimes
1. I am skillful with enjoy developing making graphs and charts.	1.63	0.56	Never
2. My notes, hand-outs, and other school materials are carefully organized.	2.00	0.59	Sometimes
3. I look familiar concepts as well as ideas that sparks my interest as I read.	2.13	0.57	Sometimes
Overall	1.92	0.57	Sometimes

Scale	Range	Description
1	1 < 1.67	Never
2	1.67 – 2.33	Sometimes
3	2.34 – 3.00	Often

Table 5: Problems in Dealing with Modular Learning

Statements	Mean	Sd	Description
1. I have received sufficient advice and guidance in relation to my module.	2.23	0.43	Sometimes
2. I was provided with timely and helpful information and guidance at the start of the module.	1.77	0.43	Sometimes
3. The aims and learning outcomes of the module were made clear to me.	2.17	0.38	Sometimes
4. Printed materials are poor quality.	1.93	0.64	Sometimes
5. Have words confused.	2.17	0.38	Sometimes
Overall	2.23	0.43	Sometimes
Overall	2.05	0.45	Sometimes

Scale	Range	Description
1	1 < 1.67	Never
2	1.67 – 2.33	Sometimes
3	2.34 – 3.00	Often

which states “Have words confused”. They signified that the respondents got the lowest mean of Sometimes (M=1.77) in the item “I have received sufficient advice and guidance in relation to my module”. Furthermore, they signified that the respondents Sometimes (OM=2.05) were surveyed in Poblacion 8 Midsayap, Cotabato.

DISCUSSION

Most of the respondents are 12 years old, male, and are studying at Lt. Andres Calungsod Elementary School Poblacion 8, Midsayap, Cotabato.

The learning style of grade 6 pupils in dealing with modular learning in terms of auditory type of learning style is practiced by most of the respondents, and they follow oral directions better than written ones. Moreover, for visual type of learning, few respondents learn well when they were given the opportunity to do it. Learning style are terms that describe how people gather, sort through, interpret, organize, draw conclusions from, and store information for later use. Student- centered approach promotes greater consistency between the teacher and the student, both of whom have a role to play in the learning process. While teachers retain authority, they now serve as facilitators, coaches, and mentors to their students (Lathan, 2021).

The learning ability of Grade 6 pupils in dealing with modular learning in terms of Digital-age literacy as type of learning ability is practice by most of the respondents. Respondents were comfortable using digital devices. Few of the grade 6 pupils stated that they are skillful with and enjoy developing and making graphs and charts. Western Sydney University (2020) defined Digital literacy as the abilities required to live, learn, and work in a society where communication and information are increasingly provided through digital platforms such as the internet, social media, and mobile devices. When you are dealing with a lot of information in numerous formats, you will need to improve your critical thinking abilities. Searching, sorting, assessing, applying, and producing knowledge all demand you to think critically.

Most of the respondents encountered problem with confusing words in the module learning while less of the respondents encountered problem in receiving sufficient advice and guidance in relation to their modules. According to the study conducted by Dangle and Sumaoang (2020), one of the key issues that arose in the study was the large number of activities in each module. Which is something the Department of Education should think about. Most of the respondents agreed that the module helped them to develop their personal skills and qualities while few of them mentioned that, the modular learning helped them save time and energy on travel to and from school. The use of modules promotes independent learning. One of the advantages of using modules for instruction

is that students develop better self-study or learning skills. Students actively participated in understanding the concepts presented in the module. They gain a sense of responsibility as they complete the tasks in the module. The students' progress on their own with little or no help from others (Dangle, Sumaoang 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that the respondents learn best when they hear something. The grade 6 pupils are digital-age literate and they are aware of various types of digital devices and they enjoy using it. The problems encountered of the respondents in dealing with Modular learning is having difficulty with terms in their modules. We are all aware that mistakes might happen sometimes. As a result, teachers and curriculum makers should consider refining the modules, and they must ensure that all lessons or activities are relevant to the learner's needs. Moreover, both parents and pupils are correct that directions in each activity must be clear enough for the pupils to grasp. Furthermore, all printed images in the modules should be legible.

REFERENCES

- Ambayon, C. M. (2020, August 12). Modular-Based Approach and Students' Achievement in Literature Ambayon *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*. Modular-Based Approach and Students' Achievement in www.journals.aiac.org.au. <http://www.journals.aiac.org.au/index.php/IJELS/article/view/6198>
- Children's Learning Styles - AbilityPath. (2020, March 10). AbilityPath; [abilitypath.org](https://abilitypath.org/apresources/childrens-learning-styles/Bernardo). <https://abilitypath.org/apresources/childrens-learning-styles/Bernardo>
- J. (July 30, 2020). Modular Learning most preferred parents: DepEd. ABS-CBNNews. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/news/07/30/20/modular-learning-most-preferred-parents-deped>
- Cabual, R. A., & Publishing, S. R. (2021, April 2). Learning Styles and Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal. Learning Styles and Preferred Learning Modalities in the New Normal; www.scirp.org. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=108297>
- Dangle, Y. & Sumaoang, J. (2020). *The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Philippine Secondary Public Schools*. Retrieved from <https://www.dpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/27-427.pdf>
- Diaz, A. (n.d.). 5 Ways to Utilize Assessment Data in the Classroom. 5 Ways to Utilize Assessment Data in the Classroom; blog.istation.com. Retrieved July 30, 2022, from <https://blog.istation.com/5-ways-to-utilize-assessment-data-in-the-classroom>
- Lathan, J. (2021). Learning Styles Modalities in the new Normal <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=108297> *Learning Styles Models Present in Textbooks* https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Learning-Styles-Models-Present-in-Textbooks_tbl5_335709318 Retrieved on November 2019
- Llego, M. (2020). DepEd Learning Delivery Modalities for School Year 2020-2021. Macmillan, F. (November 15, 2018). *Learning Styles: Kinesthetic Learner Characteristics* <https://engage-education.com/aus/blog/kinesthetic-learner-characteristics-what-are-they>
- Newton, P. M., & Salvi, A. (2001, January 1). *Frontiers How Common Is Belief in the Learning Styles Neuromyth and Does It Matter? A Pragmatic Systematic Review*. Frontiers; www.frontiersin.org. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2020.602451/full>
- Power School (August 19, 2021) Learning ability: digital-age-literacy <https://www.powerschool.com/blog/the-classroom-guide-to-digital-literacy-in-k12-education/>
- Valencia, M. R. (2022, August 27). Modular Approach in Teaching Science 10. Modular Approach in Teaching Science 10; www.ijtsrd.com. <https://www.ijtsrd.com/other-scientific-research-area/other/30318/modular-approach-in-teaching-science10/marsha-r-valencia>
- Western Governor University (January 20, 2022). *Teaching & Education Learnings About Learning Style*. Retrieved from <https://www.wgu.edu/blog/learnings-aboutlearning-styles2201>